

CONTROL OF TRANSPORT FLOW AT INTERSECTIONS WITH THE HELP OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLECT

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Abstract. At a time when modern cars are entering and being produced in our country, the increase in traffic flow in our big cities, which is the increase in traffic jams, is the main problem. It is very important to reduce and control traffic jams in cargo and passenger transportation.

According to forecasts, the population of our country will increase by 50 million by 2050, which will cause the number of motor vehicles to increase by 1.5-2 times. This article envisages the introduction of innovative transport systems used to control the movement of city and intercity vehicles, thereby saving time and reducing fuel and energy consumption. In this system, it is possible to predict the volume and flow of vehicles by collecting and analyzing data from previous years. The received information is used to control the traffic of vehicles and the timing of traffic lights. Determines the improvement of traffic efficiency and ensuring safe traffic through the use of the Traffic Management System.

Key words: Traffic oversaturation; increasing the capacity of intersections, traffic, speed of traffic, traffic incidents, traffic control; intelligent transport systems.

Anatatsiya. Yurtimizda zamonaviy avtomobillar kirib kelayotgan va ishlab chiqarilayotgan bir davrda katta shaharlarimizda transport oqimining ko`payishiga, bu esa yo`llarda tirbandliklarning ortishi asosiy muammo bo`lib kelmoqda. Yuk va yo`lovchilar tashishlarda tirbandliklarni kamaytirish va ularni nazorat qilish juda muhim hisoblanadi.

Prognozlariga qaraganda, 2050-yilga kelib yurtimiz aholisining 50 mln kishidan ortishi bu esa avtotransport vositalari sonining ham 1,5-2 barobarga ko`payishiga sabab bo`ladi. Ushbu maqolada shahar va shaharlararo transport vositalarining harakatini nazorat qilish va bu orqali vaqtini tejash, yoqilg`i-energiya sarfini kamaytirish uchun qo`llaniladigan innovatsion transport tizimlarini joriy qilish ko`zda tutilgan. Ushbu tizimda avvalgi yillardagi ma`lumotlar yig`ish va uni tahlil qilish orqali transport vositalarining hajmini va oqimini bashorat qilish imkonini beradi. Olingan ma`lumotlar transport vositalar harakatini va svetoforlarning vaqtini boshqarishda qo`llaniladi. Yo`l Harakatini Boshqarish tizimidan foydalanish orqali yo`l harakatining samaradorligini oshirish va xavfsiz harakatni ta`minlashni belgilaydi.

Kalit so`zlar: Transport oqimining haddan tashqari to`yinganligi; chorrahalarining o`tkazuvchanlik qobiliyatini oshirish, tirbandlik, harakat jadalligi, yo`l transport hodisalari, yo`l harakati nazorati; intellektual transport tizimlari.

Аннотация. В то время, когда в нашей стране появляются и производятся современные автомобили, основной проблемой является увеличение транспортного потока в наших крупных городах, а именно увеличение пробок. Очень важно уменьшить и контролировать пробки на грузовых и пассажирских перевозках.

По прогнозам, к 2050 году население нашей страны увеличится на 50 миллионов человек, что приведет к увеличению количества автотранспортных средств в 1,5-2 раза. В данной статье предусмотрено внедрение инновационных транспортных систем, используемых для управления движением городского и междугородного транспорта, что позволяет экономить время и снижать расход топлива и энергии. В этой системе можно прогнозировать объем и поток транспортных средств путем сбора и анализа данных за предыдущие годы. Полученная информация используется для контроля движения транспортных средств и времени работы светофоров. Определяет повышение эффективности дорожного движения и обеспечение безопасности дорожного движения за счет использования Системы управления дорожным движением.

Ключевые слова: Перенасыщение трафиком; увеличение пропускной способности перекрестков, трафика, скорости движения, дорожно-транспортных происшествий, регулирования дорожного движения; интеллектуальные транспортные системы.

Introduction. In recent years, great attention has been paid to scientific research in the field of transport. In particular, in order to improve the transport infrastructure, it is intended for the years 2022-2026 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan, on "Reducing accidents and deaths on the roads by

improving road infrastructure and creating safe traffic conditions, including full digitalization of the traffic management system and ensuring broad public participation in the work in this field" tasks are defined[1].

Due to the increase in the number of cars in our republic, traffic congestion is increasing sharply. This

leads to an increase in time and fuel consumption and an increase in the amount of toxic gases released into the environment. Traffic congestion is characterized by reduced speed, reduced distance between vehicles, increased travel time, and increased driver discomfort.

Traditional ways to reduce traffic congestion include expanding road traffic, improving intersections, building overpasses of different levels, and building separate lanes for buses and cars. But to build such infrastructures, a large amount of money is required. For this reason, intelligent transport systems (ITS), which require less money and are more sustainable, have been introduced abroad to reduce traffic congestion. ITS enables real-time modeling and management of traffic networks[2]. As a result of increased traffic congestion in the city, air pollution and fuel consumption have increased, and traffic efficiency has decreased. Therefore, the proposed ITS systems help to improve road monitoring and stability[3].

How do you know you're in a smart city? Simply put, you won't be stuck in traffic. Smart cities use a variety of technologies to monitor and respond to traffic conditions in real-time, reduce congestion, improve safety, and reduce the environmental impact of transportation.

To realize these benefits, cities around the world are investing in smart transportation management. A recent study by Juniper Research found that smart management

systems could save cities \$277 billion by 2025, mostly through reduced emissions and congestion. Experts predict that North American and European cities will account for more than 75% of these savings due to increased use of vehicles and increased investment in smart transportation technologies. The following stages are implemented in the management of transport flow [4].

1. Using CCTV to monitor road conditions

A closer look at the implementation of Active Traffic Management schemes in the US using this tracking system reveals that the main goal is to reduce traffic congestion and increase travel time reliability. To achieve this, a system for determining the density and speed of traffic through a network of CCTV cameras placed on the road and "loop detectors" that detect vehicles installed on the road has been introduced. Active traffic management is aimed at maximizing the effective use of the existing transport infrastructure during the day, in the case of permanent and temporary congestion. A study on controlling the use of the temporary left shoulder lane has proven to have significant environmental, economic and traffic efficiency benefits.

The vehicle flow detection system consists of wireless magneto-resistive sensors designed to detect vehicles. The sensor is installed on the road surface and transmits detection data in real time.

Picture 1. Monitoring of traffic flow through video surveillance cameras

Picture 2. Control of traffic flow by video surveillance cameras

2. Active traffic flow management and optimization methods

The main task of active traffic flow management and optimization is continuous monitoring and regulation of traffic using automated systems. Traffic conditions change over time, and accordingly, ITM systems improve safety and optimize traffic efficiency by applying dynamic traffic management strategies. Continuous monitoring and coordination of ITM systems provides a holistic approach to the management of transport facilities [5].

3. Flexible traffic light system.

Picture 3 Control of traffic lights by optimization control

4. Optimization of traffic light management

Optimization of traffic light control is done using adaptive traffic light control. This process is carried out by continuously changing the time of the traffic lights depending on the traffic. Depending on the expected flow of vehicles coming to the intersection, the traffic light will give a green light in each direction. Depending on the change in traffic flow in each period, the duration of green time allocated for each direction will change.

Picture. 3 Data processing and management in monitoring

Working area for car sensor detection: 3 meters to the sensor and 3 meters in both directions. The data received from the road sensors are transmitted through a radio channel to a radio receiver or intermediate

Intelligent traffic management system reviews for traffic congestion relief show that traffic congestion is caused by the increase in the number of vehicles on the road. This wastes time, energy and the environment. Traditional traffic lights with predetermined red and green phases are not sufficient to reduce traffic congestion, as traffic varies with peak load times of the day. City planners and urban planners prefer to implement more automated, intelligent systems that control traffic lights based on the density of vehicles on the road. For this purpose, traffic sensors are installed at intersections that monitor the density of vehicles and control traffic according to the traffic situation.

Adaptive Traffic Light Control (ATSC) improves the efficiency of the transportation system by reducing traffic congestion and extending the service life of the existing roadway[8]. This method reduces the need to add additional lanes to increase road capacity. Reduced congestion improves vehicle fuel efficiency and ultimately lowers vehicle emissions, helping to create sustainable transportation.

repeaters installed on supports. The final radio receiver collects data from the network of sensors and provides further transmission of data to the system controller using CAT5 twisted pair cables or wireless

communication over the radio channel. The received data is combined in a controller controlled by Linux OS. The data is then forwarded to a server for remote control and monitoring. The Sensys vehicle flow detection system transmits data to the server using the **FLEX-AP-D-XC** access point[9].

Traffic flow studies to evaluate the optimization of traffic light systems are usually carried out by conducting studies on a given section of road. In these studies, total travel and delay times are observed and the main types of delays are identified. The results of the study will be used to compare existing road conditions before and after improvements. Such studies are usually carried out using statistical methods and are used to evaluate traffic conditions in the past.

All sensors can be connected to a single monitoring center and display statistics and manage data collection from sensors using a convenient web interface.

ATSC (Adaptive Traffic Signal Control) works based on real-time data. Traffic sensors installed at intersections collect data and use it to optimize and update signal timing. This data is then evaluated, analyzed and new signal time improvement measures are developed. Updates will be made. This process is constantly repeated using a special program. The ATSC system communicates with each other and makes the necessary changes to the signal timing schedule for smooth traffic management. Traditional alarm time adjustment is repeated every 3-5 years. Traditional alarm timing is based on manually collected historical data. This did not take into account the unexpected daily traffic demands and resulted in high time consumption, driver dissatisfaction, customer complaints, delays and excessive human effort[9].

Traffic flow includes the use of surveillance systems and closed circuit cameras. The main purpose of ATM is to reduce time standards by reducing traffic congestion. To do this, real-time information is analyzed based on information provided to drivers.

Antennas - signal reception/transmission:

Repeaters that allow collecting data from remote sensors (more than 150 meters) and transmitting the collected data to the last radio receiver; A radio modem eliminates the wired connection and allows the master controller to establish a complete wireless data network;

The short detection radius sensor is designed for installation in special lanes, detects only bicycles and small vehicles, and can also be used to monitor the occupancy of parking spaces; We use video cameras to record traffic conditions. The traffic flow detection system is flexible and can be used on both low-volume roads and high-speed multi-lane highways, as well as tunnels and bridges. If there is interference in the propagation of radio signals near the highway, additional antennas and repeaters can be installed to guarantee a reliable continuous signal. If the road sensor signal is lost, all the data is written to its internal memory, and after the connection is restored, the received information about the events starts to be retransmitted to the server[10].

Conclusion. This paper proposes two ways to reduce traffic congestion using intelligent transportation systems. These methods include adaptive traffic control signalling and active traffic control to reduce congestion. These systems combine real-time data to efficiently use available road space and improve safety standards. Experiments on adaptive traffic control signalling have shown that this method can significantly reduce traffic congestion.

Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) are becoming more and more essential as the world develops. They make the most efficient use of the road infrastructure and reduce the need to build additional highways. By applying real-time data to traffic lights, traffic flow is improved, congestion is reduced by up to 40%, travel time is reduced by up to 25%, fuel consumption is reduced by 10%, and gas emissions are reduced by up to 22% (Radwan, 2015). The use of ITT allows government transportation agencies to collect the real-time data needed to improve transportation infrastructure, which is critical to infrastructure reform and increases accountability for those who provide it.[11]

The use of different types of sensors in the motion control system is considered. This sensor uses the IMTR-A1 radar detector to ensure that all traffic flows without stopping.

Summary. This paper proposes two ways to reduce traffic congestion using intelligent transportation systems. These methods include adaptive traffic control signaling and active traffic control to reduce congestion. These systems improve safety standards by integrating real-time data, making efficient use of available road space. The results of the experiment on the adaptive traffic control signal showed that this method significantly reduces traffic jams.

Intelligent transportation systems (ATTs) remain essential in the developing world. They make the most efficient use of road infrastructure and reduce the need to build additional highways. This improves the economic efficiency of the transport flow.

- traffic jams will be reduced by 40%.
- the time spent is reduced to 25%.
- fuel consumption is reduced by 10%.
- exhaust gases released into the environment will be reduced by 22%.

The use of different types of sensors in the motion control system is considered. This sensor will be implemented using the IMTR-A1 radar detector, so that the use of ATT can improve the transport infrastructure and ensure the uninterrupted movement of all traffic.

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